

Insect resistance

Resistance of some rice cultivars to rice gallmidge

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The entomology department of the Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology (OUAT) has screened rice cultivars for resistance to gall midge since 1970.

During the wet seasons of 1974, 1975, and 1976, lines from several crosses of resistant donors were screened under natural infestation without insecticide protection. Two replications of the rices were planted in randomized block design. Each cultivar was grown in 4-row plots 5 m long. Jaya was used as the susceptible check. Silver shoot counts were taken at 45 days after transplanting.

Of the OUAT cultures, the OR 78 series originating from the cross OR 10-35/Ptb 21 had less than 5% incidence (see table). Gall midge incidence was moderate in OR 79-3 and OR 794-1 (OR 10-35/W 1263). In the other cultures, infestation varied from 10 to 22%.

Most of the gall midge-resistant cultures from the Central Rice Research Institute were highly resistant for 3 successive years. The donor parents, including the resistant check Sakti, also harbored very low populations of gall midge. However, the CR 138 series (progeny of the cross Jaya/TKM 6) had more than 15% infestation.

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Reactions of rice cultivars to rice gall midge (mean of 1974 through 1976 wet seasons). Orissa, India.

Resistant ^a (0–5% infestation)	Cultivars rated as		Susceptible ^b (10.1–22% infestation)
	Moderately resistant (5.1–10% infestation)		
	<i>OR series</i>		
OR 78-1-2	OR 77-7-1		OR 77-1-2
OR 78-4	OR 79-3		OR 77-1-4
OR 78-8	OR 794-1		OR 77-2-1
			OR 79-5-1
			OR 79-6
			OR 80-1-2
			OR 80-2-1
			OR 80-6
			OR 80-10
			OR 80-18
			OR 93-1
			OR 93-2
			OR 93-4
			OR 95-3
			OR 95-4
			OR 96-4
			OR 96-5
	<i>CRRI series</i>		
CR 56-MR-1511-IW-1020-2	CR 56-MR-1501-IW-1016-1		CR 138-928
CR 57-MR-1023-IW-1036-2	S9-36-597		CR 139-1047
CR 57-MR-1511-IW-1028-2	CR 58-MR-1538		CR 139-1001-466
CR 57-MR-1510-IW-1024-2	CR 60-MR-1620		CR 193-1047
CR 60-MR-1539-IW-1056-1			
CR 93-MR-1024-IW-1073-1			
CR 94-MR-1624-IW-1073-1			
CR 94-MR-1550-IW-1575-E8			
CR 157-22-90			
CR 157-38943-135			
CR 157-392-21-1 85			
S5-141-461			
S6-171-121			
S6-171-388			
S7-22-527			
S8-1-717			
MR1526-1038			
MR1550-1075-690			
	<i>Donors</i>		
RPW 6-7			
RPW 9-4			
Isworakora			
W 1263			
Leaung 152			
Ptb 10			
Ptb 18			
Ptb 21			

^aSakti, the resistant check, had 3.5% infestation. ^bJaya, the susceptible check, had 22.4% infestation.